

in the '80's, is generally considered to have been better than the average who remained behind. It is not likely that the Russian Jews of 1880-90 could have yielded any such figure as is here shown for Russians of the draft army in general.

Admittedly, the draft figures do not lend themselves in most instances to a detailed and refined analysis. For the present purpose it is not at all necessary that they should. Their general trend is clear, inescapable, and incontrovertible. It shows in a most striking way that the average of American immigrants during the last

quarter of a century is below that of the native-born white population; and that the average of the countries which are sending over most of the immigrants, is even lower still. This last average is, indeed, so deplorably low that it is a fair and serious question whether the United States can eugenically afford to admit any more such average immigrants, either without any restriction, or on a percentage basis. Should not the American policy be that of admitting all who are superior to the American average, and no others?/

MANY-NODED DWARF BARLEY

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A BARLEY plant having a large number of extremely short internodes and an abundance of fine leaves was found at Aberdeen, Idaho, in the summer of 1918. It occurred in Mesa, C. I. No. 1313, an agricultural variety of *Hordeum distichon nudum*. This plant, which was very short, developed much more slowly than its neighbors, but by August 4 a single fertile slightly modified spike of nearly normal size had emerged, together with about 6 other greatly modified spikes. It was necessary to harvest the plant on this date, although the foliage was still green.

This aberrant plant (Fig. 12) which was grown under irrigation, measures about 50 centimeters from the crown to the tip of the awns. Many of the culms are branched near the base. As nearly as can easily be determined there are 17 culms, divided into 28 branches. In the original plant all the culms have more than the normal number of nodes, and roots are found on the second nodes above the crown. The spike of the original plant shown in

Figure 12 is borne upon a culm having about 12 nodes. The internodes, in general, become successively shorter toward the apex of the culm and merge into the rachis of the spike. The three lowest nodes of this spike threw off branches in place of groups of spikelets and the long intervening internodes exhibit the zigzag appearance characteristic of the lower part of the rachis of this strain. The remaining culms have many more nodes, the maximum being at least 20.

In the fall of 1918, one seed was sown in the greenhouse at Arlington Farm at Rosslyn, Va. This germinated and the resulting plant produced a number of greatly modified spikes which, in June, 1919, yielded a few seeds to add to the small original stock. The plant grew very slowly and was much taller than its parent. With the increase in height was an increase in the number of nodes, of which there were 20 to 25 on the average culm. In 1920, plants grown in the greenhouse again were very tall and again produced only greatly modified spikes. Some of the culms reached

THE ORIGINAL DWARF PLANT

FIGURE 12. The dwarf measures about 50 cm. from crown to tip of awns; the parent measures about 95 cm. There are seventeen culms divided into twenty-eight branches. (See text, p. 269.)

a height of 125 centimeters and possessed over 50 nodes. The greater lengths came from the development of vegetative branches on the inflorescence. These inflorescences often produced no fertile flowers, while frequently one or more vegetative branches at the lower nodes of the modified rachis developed into a culm similar to the original one. There is a gradual transformation of culm to rachis and of vegetative leaves to floral leaves, which it is the intention of the writers to discuss in a later paper.

One of the longer culms is unbranched for 82 centimeters and has internodal lengths ranging from 5 to 7 centimeters near the crown to 1.5 to 2.5 centimeters near the first inflorescence. One of the vegetative branches of this inflorescence is 35 centimeters long and has 29 nodes to the base of the second inflorescence. Many of these vegetative branches remained green and actively growing after the culm below had turned brown. Many attempts at crossing these greenhouse plants were made, but due to the absence of the near-normal spikes on greenhouse plants, little success attended these efforts.

Figure 13 shows a second portion of the plant with the leaves removed to show the branching which sometimes occurs at an inflorescence. Proliferations are to be seen on two of the branches. Figure 14 shows one of the modified spikes from a greenhouse plant.

Two seeds were sown in the nursery at Aberdeen, Idaho, in 1919. Both germinated and produced many-noded plants which again were only about 50 cms. tall. These plants produced many abnormal spikes containing a few seeds and two or three rather small spikes of nearly normal appearance. The culms which bore the more nearly normal spikes had fewer nodes and a much more nearly normal appearance than the others.

At Aberdeen, in 1920, plants of this dwarf form were grown which produced several nearly normal heads, and hybrids with several different varieties of barley were made successfully. In

BRANCHING AT INFLORESCENCE

FIGURE 13. In this case, branches have developed at the inflorescence. These inflorescences often produced no fertile flowers and the vegetative branches often grew to considerable length and remained green long after the remainder of the plant had turned brown.

A MODIFIED SPIKE

FIGURE 14. Great variation in the extent of abnormality of the spikes was found. In the extreme cases branches were given off at the nodes instead of spikelets; others were nearly normal. Very little seed was produced by the greatly modified spikes.

PARENT FORMS AND FIRST GENERATION HYBRIDS WITH THE DWARF BARLEY

FIGURE 15. The two parent forms on the left are Nepal and Manchuria. The type of heads obtained by crossing these two species with the dwarf form are shown on the right. No "dwarf" characteristics are found in the first generation, but in the second generation segregation of normal and dwarf forms occurred in a ratio of approximately three to one, indicating that the dwarf character is a Mendelian recessive.

1921 the Aberdeen "dwarfs" were again typical of the dwarf plants as grown outdoors in summer. One of these had 26 culms about 60 cm. long and having 12-18 nodes, and on the same plant were found 5 culms which seemed normal. None of the latter possessed more than 6 nodes above the crown, the longest was 92 cm. in height, and all five had nearly normal spikes.

The crosses were made in 1920 upon 4 varieties, as shown in Table I.

The crossed seed was grown in the greenhouse at Arlington Farm in the following winter and the F_1 heads shown in Figure 15 were obtained. No "dwarf" characteristics were found in the plants bearing these heads. The F_2 seeds from these heads were sown at Aberdeen in 1921 and produced populations which segregated for type of plant as shown in Table II.

In the Utah Winter cross, the winter plants cannot be accurately classified because of late maturity. Considering the small numbers used, the ratios obtained are in fair accordance with the expectation on a basis of a 3:1 ratio, showing the segregation of a Mendelian recessive.

Few dwarf plants have been reported in barley. Bungo Miyazama¹ reports the finding of dwarf forms in the back-cross upon Golden Melon by an F_1 plant, the offspring of a cross

between Golden Melon and the Japanese variety, Sekitori. This dwarf was heterozygous, breaking up into normals of the parental types and a still more dwarfed type in the ratio of 1:2:1. Neither of these dwarfs was at all like the one here discussed. Vestergaard² reports finding 3 dwarf-like variants in an otherwise constant line of 2-rowed barley. When crossed with Binder barley, of the 95 individuals, constituting the F_2 progeny, 81 were normal and 14 dwarf, giving a ratio of 6:1. The dwarf is not described.

In February, 1922, Dr. K. F. Kellerman, Associate Chief of the Bureau of Plant Industry, called the attention of the writers to a dwarf form of *Hordeum vulgare pallidum* which he had received from Mr. J. M. Mack of Fallbrook, Cal. Mr. Mack stated that he had discovered the type in a field two years previously. This dwarf is apparently the same type of variation as that found by the writers, but in a 6-rowed hulled barley, while that found at Aberdeen was in a 2-rowed naked barley. The double appearance of this variation seems to have one plausible explanation, namely, that it is a mutation where all the modifications which occur in the plant are caused by the same factor.

Hor³ describes what is undoubtedly the same barley as that received through Dr. Kellerman.

TABLE I. Data Regarding Barley Varieties Crossed with the Dwarf Form

Baku,	<i>H. dis. nudum</i> ,	2-rowed, bearded, naked (parental type of "dwarf").
Manchuria,	<i>H. v. pallidum</i> ,	lax 6-rowed, hulled, bearded.
Utah Winter,	<i>H. v. pallidum</i>	
	<i>pyramdatum</i> ,	very dense, 6-rowed, hulled, bearded, winter habit.
Nepal.	<i>H. v. trifurcatum</i> ,	6 rowed, naked, hooded.

TABLE II. Segregation of F_2 Generation of Dwarf Barley Crosses

Parentage	Normal	Dwarf	Ratio
Dwarf × Baku	45	14	3.21:1
Dwarf × Manchuria	49	17	2.88:1
Dwarf × Utah Winter ^a	39	8	4.88:1
Dwarf × Nepal	48	13	3.69:1
Total	181	52	3.48:1

^a In addition to the 39 normal and 8 dwarf plants, there were 5 winter plants which could not be classified.

¹ *Jour. Genetics*, 11:205-208, 1922.

² *Tidssk. Planteavl.*, 26:491-510, 1919.

³ *Science*, Vol. LV, No. 1423, April 9, 1922.